

ARTICLE

Review on Chemical-Biological Applications of Thiazole Derivatives

Nagham Mahmood Aljamali^{1*}, Manar Ghyath Abd Almutalib Almosawy^{2 †}, Ahmed Adnan Abdul Hussein^{3 ‡}, Nour Alhuda Abdul Abbas Bahar^{4 §}, Rajaa Abdul Ameer Ghafil^{5 ¶} & Noorhan Ali Hamza^{6 **}

¹Department of Chemistry, Synthetic Chemistry Field, Iraq, ²Department of Chemistry, Imam Jafar Al-Sadiq University, Najaf, Iraq, ³College of Health and Medical techniques-Kufa, University of Alfurat Al-Awsat Techniques, Iraq, ⁴Lecturer, Third Teacher in Education Ministry, Iraq, ⁵Department of Chemistry, College of Education for Girls, Kufa University, Iraq, ⁶Lecturer, Alsafwa University, College, Iraq

*dr.nagham_mj@yahoo.com. *Contributed equally.

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Abstract

This review showed many chemical methods for preparation, reactions, applications, uses of thiazole derivatives in many fields like in: coordination chemistry, analytical reagents, biological field like in antibacterial agents, antifungal agents, in a medicinal chemistry or in pharmaceutical chemistry like as a drug. The review covers possible chemical and medical applications of thiazoles derivatives.

Key words: Thiazole, Bicycles, Biological Activity, Preparation, Reactions.

Introduction

Thiazole Derivatives are planar and aromatic (pi-electron delocalization and greater aromaticity ([31],[73],[33]) than oxazoles:

Synthetic drugs belonging to the thiazolecore involve the anti-

Figure 1. Formula of Thiazole

microbial agents like sulfathiazole, penicillin,antineoplastic agents Bleomycin, Tiazofurin, anti-HIV drug, antiulcer agent. Additionally, extensively applied thiazole derivatives ([72],[66],[4],[11],[62],[40]) are the non-steroidal drug and anti-inflammatory drug Meloxicam. Thiazole derivatives have exhibited encouraging antifungal activity, microbial activity([65],[8],[3],[19],[20],[32],[1]), with marine ancestries reveal antitumor besides to antiviral activities ([7],[25],[46],[47],[58],[55],[17],[2],[45],[76],[38],[36],[39]), many other applications ([5],[60],[53],[80],[79],[48],[63],[44],[61]).

General Synthetic Routes to Thiazole Derivatives

Synthesis of Thiazole derivatives through Ring closure with reflux and Lawesson reagent.

Preparation of Thiazole Derivative Via Thione Group

By reaction between thione group from thio-compound with any carbonyl group of alkyl halide.

Figure 2. Applications of Thiazole

Figure 3. Preparation of Thiazole Derivative via Ring Closure

Figure 4. Preparation of Thiazole Derivative via Thione Group

Preparation of Thiazole Derivative Via Condensation with Thiourea

By condensation reaction to yield cycles of thiazole derivatives in Temperature more than (75 °C).

Figure 5. Preparation of Thiazole Derivative via Condensation with Thiourea

Preparation of Thiazole Derivatives via Isothiocyanate compounds

Isothiocyanate compounds Cyclize with Amine-thiol Compounds by condensation reaction at more than (75 °C).

Figure 6. Preparation of Thiazole Derivatives from Cyclization

Preparation of Thiazole Derivatives via Cyclization

Cyclization of Amine compounds with thiol Compounds by condensation reaction at more than (75 °C) with carboxyl halides.

Preparation of Thiazole Derivatives Via Thiocyanate Compounds

By reaction with thio cyanate at room temperature

Figure 7. Preparation of Thiazole Derivatives via Acyl Halides

Figure 8. Preparation of Thiazole Derivatives via Acyl Halides

General Reactions for Thiazole Compounds

There are many reactions like Electrophilic, Substitution, Oxidation Reaction.

Figure 9. General Reactions of Thiazole

Applications of Thiazole

In Coordination Chemistry as a Ligand and Complexes

Several studies described the synthesis of thiazole derivatives ([13],[6],[21],[56]) involve donated atoms like (Nitrogen, Sulfur) in their structures that participate as ligands in the coordination chemistry field ([51],[57],[43],[75],[78],[77],[26],[37]).

Figure 10. Thiazole as a Ligands and Complexes

Applications in Medical and Pharmaceutical Fields

One of the proficient and regularly applied directions of search for different active derivatives is centered on the source of privileged structures annealing in the abbreviated systems ([35],[54],[42],[59],[28]). This method includes a combination of different heterocyclic pharma-cores in one bio-compound besides to it can be successfully explained through thiazoles derivatives ([30],[10],[74],[9],[50],[27],[29],[18],[67])

Applications in Biological Fields

Thiazole moiety-including compounds linked with imine groups or azogroups ([70],[71],[15],[68],[24],[34],[16],[49],[14]) established wide application in drug for the treatment of HIV infections.

Figure 11. Thiazole Derivatives as Anticancer

Figure 12. Thiazole Derivatives against HIV infections

Figure 13. Thiazole Derivatives as Antimicrobial Reagent

Thiazole Derivatives as antifungal

Other studies discussed the inhibition and antiviral activity ([23],[64],[69],[22],[12],[52],[41]) consequence synthesis of benzothiazole derivatives linked with sulphonamide with also groups in same compounds. The thiazole derivatives have an important component

Figure 14. Thiazole Derivatives as Antifungal

impact of the pharma-cores of a great number of pharmaceutical significance bio-compounds and the estimation of their biotic action, like antibacterial, anti-tubercular, anti-fungal, besides to medical applications, is desirable, like anti-inflammatory activities. Formerly,

Figure 15. Thiazole Derivatives (anti-inflammatory)

in vitro antitumor evaluation literatures of altered (thiazole derivatives) exhibited their potent with selective nanomolar inhibitory activity contrary, to a large range of human cancerous cell lines like breast, leukemia, colon, lung, CNS, melanoma, ovarian, besides to

prostate cell lines. Human malaria transpires via transmission of

Figure 16. Thiazole Derivatives as Antitumor Agents

Plasmodium sporozoites through a taster from an infected anopheles mosquito. In scientific studies, two chemical compounds were prepared and screened against Malaria.

Figure 17. Thiazole Derivatives as Anti- Malaria

Conclusions

According to all the above, the directed search for thiazole derivatives is justified besides to promising direction in the pharmaceutical chemistry because it acts the core in many bio-molecules and many drugs.

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